

STEEL FOIL REINFORCED COMPOSITES: STUDY OF STRENGTH, PLASTICITY AND PLY SIZE EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

The objective was to study the bearing properties of steel foil and carbon fibre reinforced polymer composite (St-CFRP) laminates. Extremely thin carbon fibre plies offer an improved onset of damage and less accumulation of damage prior to ultimate failure; ply level hybridisation can enhance the bearing properties. Both effects were studied to better understand the progression of damage and effect of ply thickness. Both CFRP and Hybrid laminates of ply thicknesses 0.3 and 0.03 mm were manufactured and tested. The thin CFRP laminate has 31% higher tensile strength and a reduction in open hole strength of 28 % due to lack of delamination, critical load reached across the 0° plies more or less instantaneously. The lower delamination tendency of the thin ply composites was reflected in the open hole tensile measurements, where, the suppression of delamination resulted in higher notch sensitivity (2.26 versus 1.25). Hybridisation reduced the effects whilst increasing the open hole strength of the composite laminate further. When the bearing stress was studied, the thin CFRP laminate was observed to increase the bearing stress by 28 %. The hybrid laminates show small differences in the achieved maximum bearing stresses (circa 1,100 MPa - double that of the thick CFRP laminate), although the observed failure modes remain very different: delamination and buckling versus brittle failure. Optical analysis showed extensive plastic deformation in the joint, with evidence of good adhesion between the steel foils and thin CFRP plies. Plastic failure of the bearing joint was maintained due to the steel foils, producing a joint that may fail safely. A user subroutine was used to degrade the damaged material properties of the 3D solid model according to the Hashin failure criterion. The developed finite element models were able to recreate the observed experimental failure modes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites are heavily utilised in modern aircraft structures to minimise weight, therefore increase fuel efficiency.

The increasing use of composites in aviation and automotive industries has led to increasingly automated production methods such as pultrusion or resin transfer moulding (RTM) for cost reduction in the production of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) structures. Textile preform technologies are favourable with relatively simple geometries and constant wall thickness.

One approach is to utilise very thin ply materials (order of 0.03 mm) to locally reinforce regions of stress concentration or load introduction. Sihn et al. [1] were able to show that by adopting thinner plies, that damage initiation and progression could be significantly suppressed. However, failure modes have not been studied in detail. Previous studies by Fink and co-workers have demonstrated the potential of such ply substitution technologies [2-4] where steel was also shown to outperform Titanium as an interlayer due to its superior strength and stiffness in conventional laminated composite

materials. This study aims to understand the effect of ply size in hybrid steel - CFRP laminated composite materials.

3 MATERIALS

Prepreg, Toray M40JB, CFRP ThinPreg TM 80EP-736/CF, North Thin Ply Technology SARL was studied in this work. Two different ply areal weight; 30 g/m² (Thin) and 300 g/m² (Thick), quasi-isotropic composites were prepared using a hot press and curing at 80 °C and 6 Bar of pressure. In the hybrid laminated CFRP plates, steel foils were used to substitute the 90 ° layers in the composite, shown in Table 1.

Designation	Lay-up	Ply thickness [mm]	Density [kg/dm ³]
Thin_CFRP	[90°,45°,0°,-45°]10 _s	0.03	1.6
Thick_CFRP	[90°,45°,0°,-45°] _s	0.3	1.6
Thin_Hybrid	[St,45°,0°,-45°]10 _s	0.03	3.18
Thick_Hybrid	[St,45°,0°,-45°] _s	0.3	3.18

Table 1 Material designation and lay up that was studied.

1 EXPERIMENTAL

Optical microscopy samples of the CFRP and hybrid composites were prepared by polishing epoxy resin-embedded samples with a “TegraPol-21”, Struers GmbH, Switzerland, using progressively finer grades of emery paper at intervals of 240, 800, 1200, 2400 grit. Polishing was performed with 3 µm, 1 µm and 0.25 µm diamond polishing solutions. A “VKX-200”, Keyence, Germany, 3D laser scanning microscope was used to obtain the optical cross sectional images.

The experimental tests were performed using a Walter and Bai, Switzerland, universal testing machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell. The tensile strain in the samples was obtained using an extensometer, type “MFA-12”, Walter and Bai, Switzerland at gauge lengths of 24 mm (open hole tensile or tensile) or 50 mm (double lap bearing tests).

1.1 Tensile and open hole tensile tests

The notch sensitivity of the composites was assessed using ASTM D5766M-95, open hole tension test (H6 6 mm hole) and ISO 527-00 to obtain the tensile properties of the composite laminate (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Samples were loaded using a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min and the load, machine displacement and extensometer displacement were recorded.

1.2 Double lap bearing tests

Double lap bearing shear tests were conducted in accordance to ASTM D5961M-08, and employing 8 mm bearing fasteners (f9/H6 fit, 12.9 steel) for all tests due to the superior bearing strength of the hybrid laminates. Samples were loaded using a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min and the load, machine displacement and extensometer displacement were recorded.

2 RESULTS

Samples of each composite material were taken, and the fibre volume fraction and void content measured using ImageJ, with samples images shown in Figure 1, where the single steel foils may be readily identified in the hybrid CFRP composites. A fibre volume fraction of about 57 % was obtained for the composites, with void contents in the range 1.2 to 2.4 %.

Figure 1 Polished optical sections of the composite materials (left to right): Thick_CFRP; Thin_CFRP, Thick_Hybrid, Thin_Hybrid.

2.1 Tensile and open hole tensile tests

The thin ply CFRP composites were found to possess much higher tensile strengths, upwards of 30 % when compared to conventional composites. The notch sensitivity was calculated as the ratio of un-notched tensile strength to open hole tensile strength, and provides some indication of damage tolerance from stress concentration (in this case, a drilled hole). Noticeably higher notch sensitivity, however, was observed for the Thin_CFRP laminates, with about a factor 2.26 difference in the un-notched and notched tensile strength of the composite, see Table 2, as noted by [1].

Designation	Un-notched tensile strength [MPa]	OHT Strength [MPa]	Notch sensitivity
Thin_CFRP	742	328	2.26
Thick_CFRP	568	453	1.25

Table 2 Shows notch sensitivity of thin and thick ply CFRP composites.

The notch sensitivity that was observed was found to suppress somewhat, as would be expected, with the integration of foils, see Table 3, where the percentage difference in the mean values may be found. Noting that although the un-notched tensile strength of the Thin_CFRP is superior to the conventional Thick_CFRP, 28 % lower values for open hole tensile strength and specific open hole tensile strength were measured.

Designation	OHT Strength [MPa]	%	Specific OHT Strength [MPa.dm ³ /kg]	%
Thin_CFRP	328	- 28 %	205	- 28 %
Thick_CFRP	453	-	283	-
Thin_Hybrid	535	+ 18 %	168	- 41 %
Thick_Hybrid	589	+ 30 %	185	- 35 %

Table 3 Shows open hole strength of thin and thick ply composites.

Hybridisation of the CFRP has a far greater contribution improvement of open hole strength in the Thin_Hybrid although again, the Thick_Hybrid was found to have a higher open hole tensile strength. Significant decreases (35 and 41 %) were found in the specific strength for the hybrid materials, and

supports justification for the use of processing such as B-stage curing to locally reinforce structures only in regions of load introduction.

Noticeably different failures could be observed with the thin ply and thick ply composites, see Figure 2. In the thin-ply samples, a near horizontal crack formed through the specimen with little delamination present. The specimens with conventional laminate thickness, however, delaminated prior to failure at a large area around the hole, and often failed within the 45° layers. It may be noted that the significantly larger amount of delamination may also contribute to the relatively lower notch sensitivity of the Thick_CFRP as fibre plies align to the load direction during the delamination process. This was observed in the CFRP, as well as for the hybrid laminates. Typically failure of the composite material was noticed to occur before failure in the steel foils was measured.

Figure 2 Comparison of open hole tensile failure (left to right): Thin CFRP, Thin hybrid, Thick-CFRP and Thick_Hybrid.

2.2 Double lap bearing tests

The double lap bearing strength of the Thin_CFRP was measured to be about 28 % higher than in the Thick_CFRP composite, summarised in Table 4. The suppression of traverse cracking and delamination that was observed previously has similarly improved the bearing performance of the composite material. Both hybrid composites were found to possess much higher bearing strengths, almost double the pure CFRP composite value with virtually no penalty in weight when the specific strength was compared for these sets of tests.

Designation	Bearing strength [MPa]	%	Specific bearing strength [MPa.dm ³ /kg]	%
Thin_CFRP	720	+ 28 %	450	+28
Thick_CFRP	562	-	351	-
Thin_Hybrid	1153	+ 105 %	362	+3 %
Thick_Hybrid	1091	+ 94 %	343	-2 %

Table 4 Shows the double lap bearing strength of thin and thick ply composites.

Observing the surfaces of the tested CFRP laminates, see Figure 3, very localised damage was observed in the Thin_CFRP (seen as 22 mm delamination in the 90° layer) compared to the

Thick_CFRP, where large amounts of delamination (the order of 40 mm in the 90° layer), and fibre breakage could be seen.

Figure 3 Bearing failure in the CFRP laminates: a) Thin_CFRP, b) Thick_CFRP.

In the surface of the hybrid laminates, brittle local failure in the bearing area was observed, shown in Figure 4, compared to large deformation and out of plane buckling in the Thick_Hybrid laminates.

Figure 4 Bearing failure in the hybrid laminates: a) Thin_Hybrid, b) Thick_Hybrid.

The tested and damaged samples were embedded and sectioned where the left of the image indicates the bolt location (compression side) and the right of the image shows the damaged portion of the composite material (Figure 5 and Figure 6). From Figure 5, much localised delamination was observed in the composite, with major failure occurring in compression from the formation of kink bands in the unsupported region above the washer. The dominant failure mechanism therefore appears to be a compression, shear failure in the laminate. Within the thick laminate, delamination could be observed between all layers. Here failure appears to be much more delamination related, leading to buckling and compression of the composite material.

Figure 5 Optical cross section of bearing failure in the CFRP laminates showing: a) Thin_CFRP, b) Thick_CFRP (red boxes show washer positions).

When examining the hybrid laminates, Figure 6, each sample case was found to buckle and fail in compression/shear. Brooming is evident on the compressive side of the hole where the bolt indented

the laminate. From here, shear kink bands can be seen to reflect up the walls of the washer supported region and appear in large compress/shear damage above the washer confined region of the laminate. Delamination suppression is evident from the lack of transverse ply breakage, whilst in the case of the thick ply; much of the composite material between the steel foils has fallen out of the microscopy sample during preparation, evidence of extensive delamination and damage.

With the higher resolution images, one can see that the adhesion of the foils to the CFRP appears to be relatively good, although it must be noted that no adhesion measurements have yet been conducted for the steel-CFRP interface.

Figure 6 Optical cross section of bearing failure in the hybrid laminates showing: a) Thin_Hybrid, b) Thick_Hybrid.

3 MODELLING

A model was developed to gain understanding of the failure process and provide an assessment of the relative failure effects of the CFRP and hybrid composites. A 3D explicit damage model was developed with distinct regions within the model that were formulated individually, see Figure 7. An orthotropic material continuum model was used for a quarter model geometry using C3D8R hexagonal elements. Next a local area (red) was modelled as a layer structure with a 3D damage VUSDFLD subroutine using a Hashin 3D failure criterion [5]. The steel foil was treated as an elastic-plastic material using the Johnson Cook formulation [6] for 1.4310 austenitic stainless steel and experimental data.

Figure 7 Schematic of the developed quarter model with regions of varying complexity.

The reduction of the element stiffness through the use of field variables can be relatively easy to implement. However, they rarely correspond to a real physical aspect of the failure process. Considering the stress-dependent elongation of an element in Figure 8, a strain dependant progressive stiffness decrease was used to mimic failure of an element with more realistic softening. Therefore at each time step, the stress was computed and a Hashin 3D failure check was performed. Element stiffness was adjusted accordingly, and the load incrementation was increased.

Figure 8 Element strain dependant degradation.

The region close to the bolt was modelled as individual strips with cohesive contact fibre breakage subroutine, a damage subroutine and cohesive contact between plies, see Figure 9.

Figure 9 Geometry formulation (example of open hole tension sample for the Thick_CFRP).

Inter-ply properties were measured using double cantilever beam tests, and fitting to cohesive zone property calibration models. Next mode II and III parameters were formulated using standard relations from [7] and were formulated individually, see Figure 10. Three individual formulations were used to describe the four CFRP and hybrid laminates in this study.

Figure 10 Shows above, cohesive contact and fibre break definitions, and below, formulation of the thick, thin and single complex (Thin_CFRP sub laminate).

Stress versus strain for open hole tests compared to the simulations is shown in Figure 11. Stiffness of the simulated geometry and experiments appear to match relatively well. For the pure CFRP geometries, the failure stress is slightly under-predicted in both the Thin_CFRP and the Thick_CFRP. This may be due to lack of experimental data for all parameters in the model. Nevertheless, good description of the steel foil hybrid laminates could be achieved. From the simulations of the Thin_Hybrid, one could see an instantaneous failure (element deletion) of the 0° plies which resulted in failure of the steel plies. Whilst with the Thick_Hybrid, a steady delamination occurred, that results in significant plastic failure after delamination.

Figure 11 Plot of open hole tensile stress versus strain compared to simulations.

Interestingly, the progression of delamination is rather well replicated. The Thin_CFRP laminate is found to debond predominantly in the vicinity of the global crack, where significant fibre breakage has occurred, see Figure 12. Moreover, in the Thick_CFRP, an extended area undergoes significant delamination as was also observed experimentally.

Figure 12 Image shows above, Thick_CFRP and below Thin_CFRP laminate simulations for delamination and matrix tensile failure.

Simulations for replicating bearing tests were performed on an 8 node cluster and ran for approximately 72 hours using 20 instances.

Results for the double lap bearing tests were extremely representative of the experimental data, shown in Figure 13. In general, the constraint to delamination provided by the out of plane pressure of the washer, resulted in far less delamination. However, damage onset was suppressed for longer in the Thin_CFRP joint.

Figure 13 Plot of bearing stress versus strain for double lap shear tests compared to simulations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Novel combinations of thin ply CFRP and steel hybridisation have been evaluated. The lower delamination tendency of the thin ply composites is reflected both in the open hole tensile results and double lap bearing tests, where, interestingly, the suppression of delamination does not necessarily improve the strength. The very brittle behaviour of the Thin_CFRP results in a reduction in strength of over 25 % due to lack of delamination and critical load reached across the 0° plies more or less instantaneously. The hybrid laminates show smaller differences in the achieved maximum stresses, although the observed failures modes remain very different. With both cases, plastic failure of the joint was maintained due to the relatively high steel content, producing a joint that may fail safely.

The developed finite element models were able to re-create the observed experimental behaviours, whilst maintaining a relatively small simulation that is manageable.

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